

Managing Editor's Column

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It is quite obvious that the popularity of J.UCS is steadily increasing. This issue is already the 10th issue this year so that we are bound to exceed 12 issues in 2008. This issue is a regular issue presenting 11 papers. But of course it is not the quantity that counts, but first and foremost the quality. I am happy to report that most of the papers below have obtained much above average scores.

The papers in this issue are structured in four parts:

Part One: The articles "*Feature Selection for the Classification of Large Document Collections*" by J. Brank et al., "*Guaranteeing Seamless Mobility with User Redials and Automatic Handover Retrials*" by J.M. Gimenez et al., "*Enhancements of Meeting Information Management and Application for Knowledge Access and Learning Activities*" by C. Gütl, "*Expressibility in Sigma 1_1* " by W. Gomaa and "*An IP Core and GUI for Implementing Multilayer Perceptron with a Fuzzy Activation Function on Configurable Logic Devices*" by A. Rosado-Muñoz are regular submissions which have passed an extensive review process resulting in a number of further improvements.

Part Two: The paper "*Applications of Mash-ups for a Digital Journal*" by M.S. Khan et al. reports on interesting news features of J.UCS that I encourage you to try out yourself by going to <http://www.jucs.org:8181/mashup/>.

Part Three: The articles "*Exposure and Support of Latent Social Networks among Learning Object Repository Users*" by P. Han et al. and "*Searching ... in a Web*" by I. Witten were submitted by distinguished researchers on the occasion of the celebration "30 Years Computer Science in Graz", see e.g. <http://www.informatik.tugraz.at/cs/de/welcome/SACS>.

Part Four: The papers "*Using Taxonomies to Support the Macro Design Process for the Production of Web Based Trainings*" by A. Aqal et al., "*The Need for Formalizing Media Semantics in the Games and Entertainment Industry*" by T. Bürger and "*Image semantics: User-Generated Metadata, Content Based Retrieval & Beyond*" by M. Spaniol et al. are extensions of excellent papers from the Triple-I conference 2008. Note that this conference takes place again this year, see <http://triple-i.tugraz.at/>. The papers were selected by Klaus Tochtermann and Gisela Granitzer who comments on the papers as responsible editor as follows:

“Even though the three papers address different disciplines they have one aspect in common. All of them show how the integration of semantics can enhance various workflows and processes. The first paper addresses image semantics. Because of the increasing amount of multimedia objects on the web retrieval becomes challenging and often does not yield satisfying results. In the contribution it is shown that by combining low-level and high-level image features an image semantics is achieved that enhances retrieval results. The second paper covers a similar issue. It shows how multimedia production workflows can be improved by referring to semantic technologies. With their help the usually insufficient reusability of multimedia objects in the digital media and games industry can be enhanced. The third paper introduces a methodology which supports the collaborative authoring of teaching materials. It is based on a semantic taxonomy which helps to integrate technical and instructional skills and thus guarantees a coherent production process.”

I hope you'll enjoy the content and variety of the papers!

Cordially,

Hermann Maurer

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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